

EFFECT OF ORGANIZATIONAL JUSTICE ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE IN GOVERNMENT-OWNED POLYTECHNICS IN ANAMBRA STATE

Onyeka Chidi Okafor

Department of Entrepreneurship Studies, Faculty of Management Sciences
Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam Campus, Anambra State, Nigeria
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14925147

Abstract:

The study examined the effect of organizational justice on employee performance of government owned polytechnics in Anambra State of Nigeria. Relevant literature on organizational justice as well as employee performance was reviewed under conceptual, theoretical and empirical review. The work was anchored on justice judgment theory. A descriptive survey research design method was adopted. The target population of the study comprised 3251 employees of the government owned polytechnics in Anambra State. The sample size was 356. The sampling technique employed was a convenient sampling strategy. The structured questionnaire was used to source data from the respondents. The researcher distributed three hundred and fifty-six copies of the questionnaire but only two hundred and ninety-three valid copies were retrieved and used for the analysis. Multiple regression analysis statistical technique was used to test the hypotheses formulated to guide the study. The findings of the study revealed that procedural justice has a significant effect on employee performance of government owned polytechnics in Anambra State. It also showed that distributive justice has a significant effect on employee performance. The study also discovered that interactional justice has a significant effect on employee performance. The study recommended that management should continue to follow normal procedures and also establish good communications system with the employees especially in the decision-making process as well as organizational relations by following the principle of organizational justice. The study concluded that management efforts to increase employees' performance should be focused on relating to employees with dignity, respect and stateliness especially through leader-subordinate relations

Keywords: organizational justice, procedural, distributive, interactional, performance

1. INTRODUCTION

Organizational justice refers to an employee's perception of his/her organization's behavior, decisions and actions and how these influence his/her attitude and behavior at work. The concept was introduced by Greenberg in 1987. It entails individual or collective judgments of fairness or ethical propriety which helps to alleviate many of the ill-effects of dysfunctional work environment thereby reduces workplace stress, vindictive retaliation, employee

withdrawal and sabotage. Organizational justice as the perception of employees on the fairness of their organizations has focused on two main issues: employees' judgement on what they get, that is outcomes such as pay or promotions, and the means they obtain the outcomes, also known as procedures (Cropanzano & Greenberg, 2007). Employees are motivated and committed to work hard if they feel that their input are been appreciated and fair rewards are been justly given to them at the appropriate time. Akanbi and Ofoegbu (2013) posited that to make sure employees are committed to their tasks and duties there must be fair in its system regarding organizational justice. Organizational justice is directly related to employees' commitment and organizational commitment. This is because employees show positive behaviors such as high commitment and loyalty and disregard negative behaviors such as low commitment to work when they feel that organizations justice is fair and just. Pertinently, organizational justice in an organization cannot be underrated because it determines how the employees' performance is been assessed and rewarded.

Interestingly, previous studies on organizational justice have discovered three forms of organizational justice. The first category (distributive justice) is related to the suitability of reward or outcomes. The Second is procedural justice, which is concerned with processes, reward system or method used to distribute outcome and the third category is interactional justice, which is concerned with the relationship that prevails between workers and the management (Rahman, Haque, Elahi & Miah 2015). Ambrose (2002) stated that fairness is a very important phenomenon in individuals' everyday life particularly in job setting. Managers must take organizational justice as a core aspect in their everyday activities because of its advantage in increasing employees' commitment and indirectly reduces employees' turnover (Elanain, 2009). However, organizational justice creates enormous benefits for organizations and employees including greater trust and commitment (Cropanzano, Bowen & Gilliland, 2007).

Most employees in Nigerian polytechnics have shown low commitment to work which has led to absenteeism, job insecurities, low employee turnover rate and frequent incidences of industrial actions (Yavus, 2010). Similarly, Mbwiria (2010) has posited that a low level of organizational commitment among employees in Nigeria has taken a perturbing trend. Furthermore, Yavus (2010) stated that the growing rate of competitiveness' among polytechnics has forced management to compete for competent employees which will give the institution an edge over the others. Notwithstanding that effective strategies have been developed to curb shortcomings of organizational justice in higher institutions in Anambra State but they are still faced with all these challenges. It is against this backdrop that the study sought to examine the extent to which organizational justice affects employee's performance in government owned polytechnics in Anambra State.

Objectives of the study

The main objective of the study is to investigate the effect of organizational justice on employee performance of government owned polytechnics in Anambra State of Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study are to:

1. Determine the effect of procedural justice on employee performance.
2. Examine the effect of distributive justice on employee performance.
3. As certain the effect of interactional justice on employee performance.

Research Questions.

The following research questions are raised in the course of this study

1. To what extent does procedural justice affect employee performance?
2. To what extent does distributive justice affect employee performance?
3. To what extent does interactional justice affect employee performance?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study

HO₁: Procedural justice has no significant effect on employee performance.

HO₂: Distributive justice has no significant effect on employee performance.

HO₃: Interactional justice has no significant effect on employee performance.

Significance of the Study

This study is expected to assist business leaders and human resource practitioners in their understanding of the key drivers of employee performance in the institutions. The study is expected to provide which will serve as insights for learning and development for practitioners. The study will also enable them to examine how organizational justice efforts is a key component towards a more engaged workforce and may perhaps trigger initiatives that enhance employees' justice perceptions of their institutions. In addition, this study is expected to provide additional insights in order to broaden the body of knowledge especially on organizational justice and employee performance. Also, the study is expected to provide reference materials for further research on organizational justice and employee performance.

2. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE**2.1 Conceptual Review****2.1.1 Organizational Justice**

The concept of organizational justice was introduced in 1987 by Greenberg. It is concerned with how an employee judges the behavior of the organization as well as the resultant attitude and behavior of the employee. It simply refers to the extent of employee perception of fairness in the workplace. Organizational justice has been widely studied in the majors of management, psychology and organizational behavior (Parker & Kohlmeyer, 2005).

Similarly, organizational justice is the expression of workers view about fair treatment in the organization and a building block for strong tied between worker and management of the organization (Greenberg, 2017). It deals with how workers perceived they are been treated which if positive leads to commitment and loyalty to their job

tasks, duties and organizational goals but if negative leads to employee absenteeism, turnover. Cohen-charash and Spector (2011) have posited that areas of concern in organizational justice include; performance, commitment, loyalty, job satisfaction, citizenship behavior, employee turnover, employee theft and alienation. Organizational justice is the measurement of an organization's conduct towards its workers by taking into account the general ethical and moral norms (Rahman, Haque, Elahi & Miah, 2015). Syarifah (2016) has viewed organizational justice as the fair treatment to employees which is divided into three types: distributive justice, procedural justice and interactional justice. Consequently, the relationship between organizational justice and job performance is not only dependent on job tasks but also involves interpersonal elements and motivations which also contribute to job. In addition, employees compare their benefits and rewards between employees within or outside the related organizations and if there are variations between both this can lead to a worrying trend of absenteeism, disloyalty, high rate of turnover, low commitment which adversely affect organizations productivity and profit.

Employee performance

Employee performance is multi-faceted in nature and the link between performance and justice has a long history and both have been found to be closely related. Employee performance has been divided into mainly in-role performance or task performance and extra role performance or contextual performance (Muhammad, Muhammad, Anum & Samina, 20 17). In role or task performance can be described as employee competency to fulfill the tasks and responsibilities delegated in his/her job description while extra-role performance or contextual performance is employee's extra efforts in performing tasks that have no direct relationship to the main job descriptions and improve the quality of social relationships with between the employees and management (Faruk, 2016). Employee performance can be said to be the quality and quantity of output put in by employees towards the success of the organization. Orishede and Bello (2019) maintained that performance should be assessed through the contributions of employees to the organization during a particular time period. Also, it should be based on a competency model that focuses on the skills needed by employees in both present and future. Notwithstanding that there are inadequate empirical research on the relationship between organizational justice and employee performance. Cohen-Charash and Spector (2001) maintained that major determinant of employee performance is procedural justice, with distributive and interactive justice having almost no impact on employee performance. However, distributive, procedural and interactional justices have significant and positive impacts on self-rated performance and supervisor-rated performance (Faruk, 2016). Therefore, organizational justice must co-exist in the organization goals so as to encourage utmost employee performance. Also, work should be consistent with the assessment of the organization management and organizational justice which will reduce turnover, absenteeism, low commitment, low morale and low job satisfaction (Syarifah, 2016).

Procedural Justice

Procedural justice is seen as the procedures used in making decisions concerning compensation structure (such as fairness in salaries and job systems) within the organization as a whole. Procedural justice plays an important role in shaping people's perceptions and has led to a stronger focus among justice researchers and practitioners on issues of procedural justice (Folger & Konovsky, 2019). Procedural justice maintains that policies, procedures used by management in decision making must be consistent, accuracy in information gathering, unbiased and impartial and must represent employee's interests. In his contribution, Taamneh (2015) maintained that procedural justice is the degree to which employees are treated with politeness, dignity, and respect by managers while applying formal procedures. It also determines the outcomes and explanations provided to them which convey information about why procedures were used in a certain way or why outcomes were distributed in a certain fashion. It seems to have a positive influence on employee commitment which reduces employee turnover as well as absenteeism.

Furthermore, Khatbeh, Mohamed and Rahman (2020) observed that procedural justice includes how procedures and process concerning decisions about the design and management of internal structures (such as salary and wage structure) are made, balanced and consistent which must be understood and accepted by employees because the process of applying these procedures is continuous and involves all employees; employees have a role to play in this process; employees have the right to appeal the results; accuracy of data used in the process because according to Adam's theory of equity, where the ratio of inputs to outputs must be fair in order to increase job satisfaction and improve performance. Moazzezi, Sattari and Bablan (2014) in a research called the interchange of justice and employees' performance; studying the relationship between the organizational policies and procedural justice where the impact of procedural justice on the employees' performance has been studied, the results showed that procedural justice is related to the duty function and context function. Azubuike and Madubochi (2021) postulated that when an employee feels that the procedures used in making decisions regarding the distribution of rewards, such as promotion is just and fair, it leads to increased positive personal outcomes, especially job satisfaction and commitment to an organization but if employees perceive that the decision making process concerning salary and wage structure is unfair and discriminated will lead to psychological stress and real sickness leading to absenteeism and job accidents and can indirectly affect the goals and objectives of the organization in a negative way.

Distributive Justice

Distributive justice is concerned with what persons obtain. It refers to as the fairness of the outcomes received as a result of an allocation decision (Cropanzano & Greenberg, 2007). This implies that when an employee perceives high fairness in the outcome of their performance, they tend to contribute immensely to the organizational goals and objectives. Distributive justice deals with outcomes related to job which affects individuals' attitude like job

satisfaction when the allocation of resources is fair and just and negative influence on turnover intentions if there is discrimination in the allocation of resources. In order to achieve distributive justice, both rewards and punishments should be perceived as being impartially allocated as any sense of unfairness in this regard results in employees exerting less effort in their organizational participation (Biswas & Ramaswami, 2013). Similarly, distributive justice represents employee perception of fairness of the outcome that they receive from the organization such as pay, recognition, promotion, performance appraisal and rewards which can be distributed based on needs, equity or contributions individual employees can determine the level of fairness of the distribution through comparison with others. Also, when these results are considered unfair, individuals would cognitively distort input and outcome from themselves or others (Harif, Dara & Hendra, 2019). Moreover, Aryee, Budhwar and Chen (2002) found similar results in their study of employees of a public sector organization in India whereby distributive justice correlated with trust in organization, job satisfaction, turnover intentions, organizational commitment and organizational citizenship behaviors. Distributive Justice exhibits the positive perception of employees toward rewards such as compensation or promotions as per their expectations. It is the intended equality regarding results as appropriate imbursement against employee efforts and opportunities for career advancement (Paracha, Azeem, Malik & Yasmin, 2017).

Interactional Justice

Interactional justice is the one of the recent dimension of organizational justice. It refers to as people's sensitivity to the quality of interpersonal treatment they receive during the enactment of organizational procedures (Greenberg, 2012). Interactional justice comprises of two sub-dimensions; interpersonal justice and informational justice. Interpersonal justice talks about treating individuals with kindness, dignity, respect and esteem particularly in the relationships between employees and managers. Informational justice, on the other hand, is about informing employees properly and correctly in matters of organizational decision making (Faruk, 2016). The difference between interpersonal and informational justice lies in the different aspects of communication, in that, interpersonal justice can be seen to focus on the 'how' of the communication, that is the courteousness and respectfulness of it whereas informational justice can be said to focus on the 'what' of the communication, that is, the honesty and truthfulness of the information (Colquitt, 2012). In addition, Ajala (2015) has identified some key points of interactional justice which can enhance people's perceptions of fair treatments. They are; truthfulness by giving realistic and accurate information; respect, i.e. employees must be treated with dignity; statements and questions should never be improper or involve prejudicial elements such as racism or sexism; justification. Furthermore, when a perceived injustice has occurred, giving explanation or apology can reduce or eliminate the sense of anger generated. Though most researchers have not always agreed on the dissimilarity between procedural and interactional justice and a study by Cropanzano et al. (2012) suggested that there is indeed a distinction between procedural and interactional justice

and argues that although they are correlated, they should be treated as separate constructs as they have different consequences.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on justice judgment theory propounded by Leventhal (1980). The theory states that when the employees perceive the organizational procedures as being fair and just, they tend to be more committed and loyal. But when the employees perceive the organizational procedures as being unfair and unjust, they tend to retaliate through resentment and anger. The assumption of this theory is that when the employees feel that they are treated well, fair and just, their inputs such as commitment, handwork, loyalty matches their output such as rewards, bonuses, pay. The theory posits that individuals proactively employ justice to make rationalization, resources allocation and decision making. The theory postulates that absence of resentment and anger will lead to increased employees' commitment, loyalty and performance. This theory also encourages employee perceptions of fairness and equity as well as promotes employees' commitments and maintenance of long-term relationship with the organization.

Review of Empirical Studies

Ajala (2019) examined the influence of organizational justice on job satisfaction of employees in the manufacturing sector in Ogun State of Nigeria. The descriptive research design was adopted using an ex-post facto research design method. The population of the study comprised the staff of five manufacturing firms in Ogun State, Nigeria. The main instrument used for the study was the questionnaire designed on a 4-point rating scale ranging from strongly agree (SA) = 4 to strongly disagree (SD) = 1. The average reliability index of the research instrument was 0.870. Also, the generated data were presented and analyzed while Pearson correlation was used to test the formulated hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The study found strong relationships among the three dimensions of organizational justice studied and job satisfaction in the following descending order; distributive justice ($r = 0.955$); procedural justice ($r = 0.968$) and interactional justice ($r = 0.966$). The implication of the study was that the level of job satisfaction is a direct response to the perceived existence of organizational justice at the workplace.

Ogwuche, Musa and Nyam (2018) investigated the influence of perceived organizational justice on job performance among secondary school teachers in Makurdi metropolis. A total of 188 secondary school teachers were drawn from Makurdi metropolis. Organizational justice scale which was developed by Nerinhoff & Moorman (1993) was used in the study. The demographic data revealed that 106 (56.4%) were males and 79(42.0%) were females. The findings from the study showed that perceived organizational justice significantly and positively influence job performance. The findings also indicated that organizational climate did not significantly influence job performance among secondary school teachers $F(1,181) = .103, P > .05$. The finding

also discovered that perceived organizational justice and organizational climate significantly and jointly influence job performance among secondary school teachers in Makurdi.

Evawere, Eketu and Needorn (2018) conducted a study on the relationship between organizational justice and workers' citizenship behavior in Port Harcourt. The study utilized cross-sectional survey research design. The study used copies of the questionnaire to collect the primary data needed for the study. The study found that strong correlation exists between the dimensions of organizational justice and measures of workers' citizenship behavior. The study recommended that organizational managers should view their functions and actions as messages that affect employees' fairness perceptions. It was also recommended that employers looking for exceptional performance should treat their employees fairly for improved productivity.

Gichira (2016) investigated the influence of organizational justice perceptions on commitment of employees in health sector organizations in Kenya. The study adopted a descriptive and correlation research designs. Justice perceptions were measured using Colquitt's four-construct model comprising of distributive, procedural, interpersonal and informational justice while commitment was measured through Meyer's three component model comprising of affective, continuance and normative commitment. Inferential statistics comprising of correlation, multiple linear regression models and ANOVA analysis were applied to establish the relationship between the independent and dependent variables. The generated data were analyzed through the use of copies of the questionnaire. The findings of the study showed that distributive justice perceptions, procedural justice perceptions, interpersonal justice perceptions and informational justice perceptions had significant relationships with affective, continuance and normative commitment in health sector nongovernmental organizations in Kenya. The study findings provide support to the contention that employees evaluate their employer/employee interactions from a justice perspective and interpret the experience as just or unjust treatment.

Faruk and Yil (2016) investigated the impacts of three aspects of organizational justice, namely, distributive justice, procedural justice and interactional justice on the task performance of employees in Turkey. The study was conducted based on data collected from 942 teachers working in public schools in three Turkish metropolitan cities. The hypotheses were tested using partial least squares structural equation modeling techniques. The findings of the study indicated that among the three aspects of organizational justice, distributive justice has a positive and significant impact on task performance. However, it was determined that the other two aspects, procedural justice and interactional justice had no significant impact on employee task performance in Turkey.

Karanja (2016) investigated the influence of organizational justice on organizational commitment of teachers in public secondary schools and bank tellers in commercial banks in Kenya. The study adopted a correlation research design. The study population included 63,933 teachers in the 47 Counties and bank tellers in commercial banks in Kenya. A random sample of 382 teachers was drawn from three purposively selected Counties. The Nairobi head office of each bank was purposively sampled for commercial banks. A sample of 140 tellers was selected

using simple random sampling. Data were collected using structured questionnaire. Data analysis involved statistical computations of means, percentages, correlation and multiple regression analysis. The findings of the study reported that teachers' organizational justice significantly and positively influenced teacher's organizational commitment. Distributive justice and interpersonal justice were found not to be significant predictors of organizational commitment while procedural and informational justice were found to be significant predictors of organizational commitment for teachers in Kenya.

3. METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a cross-sectional survey research design method. The geographical area of the study is Anambra State of Nigeria. The study used primary source of data collection method through the use of copies of the questionnaire. The target population of study comprised the employees of Federal Polytechnic Oko (3013) and Anambra State Polytechnic, Mgbakwu (238), thus totaling 3251; sourced from the personnel units of the respective Polytechnics (2021). The sample size of the study was 356 while a convenience sampling strategy was adopted. The validation of the research instrument was done through face and content validity. Three research experts were given the instruments for scrutiny and corrections. Their suggestions and remarks were reflected in the main instrument of the study. The reliability of the instrument was established through a pilot study using a test-retest method. The pilot test was conducted by using ten copies of the questionnaire, administered to ten pilot respondents at two different points in time at an interval of two weeks. Their responses on both the first and second administrations were collated, compiled, compared and correlated using the Cronbach alpha correlation coefficient. The coefficient value of 0.793 proved the reliability and internal consistency of the research instrument appropriate for the main survey. The study adopted a multiple regression analysis technique and tested the 3 hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

4. DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Gender	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	130	44%
Female	163	56%
Age	Frequency	Percentage (%)
20-45	131	45
46-55	98	33
56-70	64	22
Marital Status	Frequency	Percentage
Single	117	40

Research Article

Married	173	59	
Divorced	3	1	
Educational Level	Frequency	Percentage	
SSCE	64	22	
OND / HND	109	37	
B.A/ B.SC	65	22	
M.SC	55	19	
Years of Experience	Frequency	Percentage	
5-9	164	56	
10-14	83	28	
15-19	35	12	
2021 20 and above	11	4	Source: Field Survey,

A total of three hundred and fifty-six (356) copies of the questionnaire were distributed to the respondents. Two hundred and ninety-three copies of the questionnaire (293) were properly filled and found valid for analysis. Table 1 demonstrates the profile of the respondents.

Table 1 also shows that 130 (44%) of respondents are male, while 163 (56%) of the respondents are female. This indicates that a majority of the respondents are female. Table 1 shows that 45 % of the respondents are within the ages of 20 - 45 years old. 33 % of respondents are between 46 – 55 years old and 22 % are between 56 – 70 years old. The data represented in the table implies that majority of workers in the survey are between 20-29 years old. Table 1 also shows that 40 % of workers are single, while 59 % are married and only 1 % is divorced. Therefore, it is deduced that majority of workers are married. Table 1 also presents the educational qualification of the employees. It can be seen that majority of workers (37%) are OND/HND holders whereas minority of the workers possess M.Sc. certificates. This indicates that majority of the workers were literate enough to understand and properly respond to the questionnaire items with limited guidance. Table 1 also shows the years of work experience of the respondents. Information obtained reveal that 56 % of workers have 5-9 years of working experience, 28% have between 10- 14 years of experience, 12% have between 15 -19 years and experience and finally, 4% have 20 years and above of experience. The percentages show that majority of respondents have a maximum 9 years of working experience.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of the Study

	Mean	Std. Deviation
EP	1.3491	.47740
PJ	1.6065	.62268
DJ	2.5651	.74505

Table 5: Multiple Regression Coefficients Result

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	T	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
	B	Std. Error				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Constant	1.551	.153		10.111	.000	1.249	1.853
PJ 1	.279	.036	.364	7.761	.000	.350	-.208
DJ	.190	.031	.296	6.112	.000	.129	.251
IJ	.058	.021	.145	2.836	.005	.099	-.018

Dependent variable: employee performance

NB: Procedural Justice (PJ), Distributive Justice (DJ), and Interactional Justice (IJ). **Source:** SPSS Output, 2021. A closer look at table 3 indicates that the F- statistics which is used to test for the overall fitness of the regression model has a value of 40.530. The corresponding probability value of F-statistics is 0.000 which is less than 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, we accept the model and state that the regression model fit well with the data used in this study. A careful examination of table 4 portrays that the coefficient of determination explains the percentages, proportion or total amount of variations in the dependent variables as a result of changes in the independent variables in the model. From our regression result, R^2 is 0.627 (62.7%). The closer its values are to 1 the better the fit since the value is usually 0-1. This implies that the independent variables can explain about 63% of the changes in the dependent variable, leaving the remaining 37% which would be accounted for by other variables not included in the model.

Furthermore, coefficients indicate the signs and magnitude of the parameters used in the study. Based on table 5, Procedural justice (PJ) has a positive sign given its value as 0.279. This implies that a unit increase in Procedural justice (PJ) increases employee performance by 27.9%. Distributive justice (DJ) has a positive sign and its value is 0.190; this implies that a unit increase in Distributive justice (DJ) increases the employee performance by 19%. Interactional Justice (IJ) has a positive sign and its value is 0.058; this implies that a unit increase in Interactional Justice (IJ) increases the employee performance by 5%. Table 5 also shows the T- Statistics: which is used to measure the significance of individual explanatory variables in the model. That is to find out the significant effect of the explanatory variables on the dependent variables at 0.05 level of significance. Based on table 5 result, it was discovered that procedural justice has a t-value of 7.761 and p-value of 0.000, distributive justice has a t-value of 6.112 and p-value of 0.000, while interactional justice has a t-value of 2.836 and p-value of 0.005. All are statistically significant. This shows that they significantly affect employee performance. In addition, Procedural, distributive and interactional justice are positively significant at 5% level. This implies that

they contribute significantly and positively to employee performance in government owned polytechnics in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Test of Hypotheses Hypothesis One

HO: Procedural justice has no significant effect on employee performance of government owned polytechnics in Anambra State, Nigeria.

HA: Procedural justice has a significant effect on employee performance of government owned polytechnics in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Drawing inference from our regression result in table 5, we found that the t-value of procedural justice is 7.761, while its probability is 0.000. Decision: since its probability (0.000) is less than 0.05% level of significance, we reject the null hypothesis (HO) and accept alternative hypothesis (HA) which says that Procedural justice has a significant effect on employee performance of government owned polytechnics in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis Two

HO: Distributive justice has no significant effect on employee performance of government owned polytechnics in Anambra State, Nigeria.

HA: Distributive justice has a significant effect on employee performance of government owned polytechnics in Anambra State, Nigeria.

In addition, considering table 5 result, we find out that the t-value for distributive justice is 6.112 while its probability is 0.000. This shown that the distributive justice is positively significant at 5% level of significant. Decision, we accept (HA) and reject (HO). This implies that distributive justice has a significant effect on employee performance of government owned polytechnics in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis Three

HO: Interactional justice does not have a significant effect on employee performance of government owned polytechnics in Anambra State, Nigeria.

HA: Interactional justice has a significant effect on employee performance of government owned polytechnics in Anambra State, Nigeria.

From table 5, we find out that the t-value for interactional justice is 2.836 while its probability is 0.005. Our decision is to accept (HA) and reject (HO). This implies that interactional justice has a significant effect on employee performance of government owned polytechnics in Anambra State, Nigeria.

6. Summary of Findings

1. Procedural justice has a significant effect on employee performance in government owned polytechnics in Anambra State of Nigeria.
2. Distributive justice has a significant effect on Employee performance in government owned polytechnics in Anambra State of Nigeria.

3. Interactional justice has a significant effect on Employee performance in government owned polytechnics in Anambra State of Nigeria.

7. Conclusion and Recommendations

Organizational justice as one of the key indicators associated with employees' willingness to go above and beyond their job requirements. Management efforts to increase employees' performance should be focused on treating employees with dignity, respect and stateliness especially through leader-subordinate relations. The present study enjoins management in polytechnics to appreciate the need to treat valuable employees in a fair with more emphasis on interactional justice so as to increase employees' sense of engaging in citizenship behaviours that benefits the organization as a whole. Organization might improve employee performance by taking into account components of organizational commitment and job satisfaction. Employee who is more satisfied with their work will show more involvement into their work that incorporate continuous quality improvement into their activities and encourage them to participate in achieving organization goals. Therefore, the study recommends that;

1. Management should follow fair and reasonable procedures in order to establish a good communication system with the workers in the decision-making process as well as organizational relations.

2. Organizations should try to provide the possibility of appeal for employees who feel unfairly treated, by ensuring employees ethical standards for improved performance.

3. Organizational managers should see their functions and actions as messages and communications that have undertone in order to model better employees' fairness perception.

8. References

Ajala, E. M. (2019). Organizational justice and job satisfaction among industrial employees in Ogun State, Nigeria. *African Journal of Social Work*, 5(1), 23-33.

Ajala, E. M. (2015). The influence of organizational justice on employees' commitment in manufacturing firms in Oyo State, Nigeria: Implications for industrial social work. *African Journal of Social Work*, 5(1), 93.

Akanbi, K., & Ofoegbu, O. (2016). Impact of perceived organizational justice on organizational commitment of a food and beverage firm in Nigeria. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 3(14), 207-218.

Amah, E. (2015). Distributive justice and employees' commitment to supervisor in selected hospitals in Rivers State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 2321-8916.

Ambrose, M. (2002). The role of overall justice judgments in organizational justice research: A test of mediation. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 94(2), 491-500.

- Aryee, S., Budhwar, P. S., & Chen, Z. X. (2002). Trust as a mediator of the relationship between organizational justice and work outcomes: Test of a social exchange model. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 23(3), 267–285.
- Azubuike, E. S., & Madubochi, W. (2021). Procedural justice and employees' commitment in selected hospitals in Rivers State. *African Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities Research*, 4(2), 49-58. Retrieved from www.abjournals.org
- Biswas, S., Varma, A., & Ramaswami, A. (2013). Linking distributive and procedural justice to employee engagement through social exchange: A field study in India. *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 24(8), 1570–1587.
- Cohen-Charash, Y., & Spector, P. E. (2001). The role of justice in organizations: A meta-analysis in Makurdi metropolis of Benue State. *Management and Organizational Studies*, 5(2), 16-26.
- Colquitt, J. (2012). Organizational justice. In S. Zedeck (Ed.), *The Oxford handbook of organizational psychology* (pp. 526–547). Oxford University Press.
- Cropanzano, R., Bowen, D., & Gilliland, S. (2007). The management of organizational justice. *Academy of Management Perspectives*, 5(8), 34-48.
- Cropanzano, R., & Greenberg, J. (2007). Progress in organizational justice: Tunneling through the maze. *International Review of Industrial and Organizational Psychology*, 12(1), 317-372.
- Elanain, H. (2009). Job characteristics, work attitudes, and behaviors in a non-western context: Distributive justice as a mediator. *Journal of Management Development*, 28(5), 457-477.
- Evawere, J. L., Eketu, C. A., & Needorn, R. (2018). Organizational justice and workers' citizenship behavior: A study of hotels in Port Harcourt. *International Journal of Advanced Academic Research in Social and Management Sciences*, 4(5), 103-117.
- Faruk, K. (2016). The impact of organizational justice on employee performance: A survey in Turkey and Turkish context. *International Journal of Human Resource Studies*, 6(1), 1-11.
- Folger, R., & Konovsky, M. A. (2019). Effects of procedural and distributive justice on reactions to pay rise decisions. *Academy of Management Journal*, 32(1), 115–130.

- Gichira, P. M. (2016). Influence of organizational justice on commitment of employees in health sector non-governmental organizations in Kenya (Doctoral dissertation, Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology).
- Greenberg, J. A. (2017). Taxonomy of organizational justice theories: The academy of resource in industrial organizations in South-West Nigeria. *Global Advanced Research Journal of Management and Business Studies*, 1(6), 201-209.
- Harif, A. R., Dara, Y. R., & Hendra, L. (2015). Distributive justice, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment as antecedents of employee performance: A study in Indonesia National Health Insurance Workers. *Advances in Economics, Business and Management Research*, 100.
- Karanja, G. W. (2016). Effect of organizational justice on organizational commitment in public secondary schools and commercial banks in Kenya (Doctoral dissertation, Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology).
- Khtatbeh, M. M., Mohamed, M., & Rahman, S. (2020). The mediating role of procedural justice on the relationship between job analysis and employee performance in Jordan Industrial Estates. School of Business and Economics, Universiti Putra Malaysia, 43400, UPM Serdang, Selangor DarulEhsan, Malaysia.
- Leventhal, G. S. (1980). What should be done with equity theory? New approaches to the study of fairness in social relationships. In K. Gergen, M. Greenberg, & R. Willis (Eds.), *Social exchange: Advances in theory and research* (pp. 27-55). Plenum.
- Mbwiria, K. (2010). Influence of principals' leadership styles on teachers' career commitment in secondary schools in Imenti South District in Kenya (Master of Education in Education Management thesis, Chuka University College).
- Moazzezi, M., Sattari, S., & Bablan, A. Z. (2014). Relationship between organizational justice and job performance of Payamenoor University employees in Ardabil Province. *Singaporean Journal of Business Economics and Management Studies*, 2(6).
- Muhammad, Z. I., Muhammad, R., Anum, F., & Samina, N. (2017). The impact of organizational justice on employee performance in public sector organizations in Pakistan. *International Journal of Economics and Management Sciences*.

- Muzumdar, P. (2012). Influence of interactional justice on the turnover behavioral decision in an organization. *Journal of Behavioral Studies in Business*, 5(1), 34–41.
- Ogwuche, C. H., Musa, M. H., & Nyam, J. (2018). Influence of perceived organizational justice and organizational climate on job performance among secondary school teachers in Makurdi metropolis. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 86(2), 278–321.
- Orishede, F., & Bello, A. (2019). Relationship between organizational justice and employees' performance. *Nigerian Journal of Management Sciences*, 7(1).
- Paracha, A. T., Azeem, M., Malik, S., & Yasmin, R. (2017). Impact of organizational justice on employee performance: Mediating role of emotional intelligence: An analysis of public sector organizations in Pakistan. *Global Development in Humanities, Education, and Civilization (GDHEC 2017)*.
- Parker, D. J., & Kohlmeyer, J. M. (2005). Organizational justice and turnover in public accounting firms: A research note. *Accounting, Organizations and Society*, 30(1), 357-367.
- Syarifah, H. B. A. (2016). Impact of organizational justice on employee intrinsic and extrinsic performance: A case study in Kota Kinabalu Polytechnic, Malaysia. *Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review*, 5(11). Retrieved from www.arabianjbmr.com
- Taamneh, A. M. (2015). Impact of practicing procedural justice on employees' organizational citizenship behavior in the Jordanian Ministry of Justice. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 6(8).
- Yavuz, M. (2010). The effects of teachers' perception of organizational justice and culture on organizational commitment. *African Journal of Business Management*, 4(5), 695-701.